

Proof for the Vasilenkova Equation - Update 2.0. (Sophia Vasilenkova)

$$\left(\frac{9.81m/s^2 \cdot M}{10} \right) \cdot 11$$

= = F (N)

9.81m/s ²	Derived by using Newton's law of universal gravitation, and Newton's second law of motion. Due to this being Earth's gravitational acceleration, the formula will only be true on Earth.
M	Variable - mass of the object the force is exerted upon.
10 (integer)	Given value - to create 10% - 10% is the universal engineering standard which accounts for a variety of variables, such as air resistance, non-laminar (turbulent) flow around an object, friction and other non-specific variables. When represented by 10%, the answer is approximate, but accurate enough to be true. This will be explained later in the proof.
11 (integer)	Given value - to create 10% - 10% is the universal engineering standard which accounts for a variety of variables, such as air resistance, non-laminar (turbulent) flow around an object, friction and other non-specific variables. When represented by 10%, the answer is approximate, but accurate enough to be true. This will be explained later in the proof.
Assumption 1	Air resistance, friction and turbulence will be in 10%, which is not true, however can give an accurate answer.
Assumption 2	The amount of turbulent flow and air resistance is equal around the object.
= F (N)	Force is given in Newtons, which is an Adaptation from F=ma (Isaac Newton).

Formulae used to construct this formula	F=ma (Newton's second law of Motion), Newton's law of universal gravitation.
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9.81m/s² = acceleration

M = mass

10 = Given to find 10%

11= Given to find 10%

$$\left(\frac{9.81m/s^2 \cdot M}{10} \right) \cdot 11$$

$$= F(N)$$

F(N) is the weight of the object, or the force it is exerting on the Earth's surface.

An example:

$$9.81m/s^2 \times 40 = 392.4$$

$$= 392.4/10 \times 11$$

$$= 431.64 \text{ N Down}$$

Using F=ma and manual multiplication

$$AxM = 9.81m/s^2 \times 40$$

$$= 392.4$$

$$392.4/10$$

$$= 39.24$$

$$39.24 \times 11$$

$$= 431.64 \text{ N}$$

This proves that the Formula is accurate.

That 110% of mass multiplied by acceleration is accurate.

Therefore, $9.81\text{m/s}^2 \times M_{10 \times 11}$ has been proven, representing the force in Newtons, after mass is multiplied by acceleration and resistance, turbulent flow and other variables have been added to the outcome. QED. ■